

Factors Related to Being Good Membership Behavior in Organization of Personnel at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

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Abstract—The aims of this study were to compare the differences of being good membership behavior among faculties and staffs of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University with different sex, age, income, education, marital status, and working period, and investigate the relationships between organizational commitment and being good membership behavior. The research methodology employed a questionnaire as a quantitative method. The respondents were 305 faculties and staffs of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. This research used Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test, One-Way ANOVA Analysis of Variance, and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in data analysis. The results showed that organizational commitment among faculties and staffs of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University was at a high level. In addition, differences in sex, age, income, education, marital status, and working period revealed differences in being good membership behavior. The results also indicated that organizational commitment was significantly related to being good membership behavior.

Keywords—Being Good membership behavior, Organizational Commitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS the public enterprise sector has played a significant role in accomplishing development objectives in developing countries. Governments are managing and expanding the education organizer sector with the intention of promoting and accelerating national development. These public enterprises operate in all development sectors of nations, including public utilities and energy. The organizer sector in Thailand has been one of the most important sectors, because the country depends largely on imported energy at a considerable cost each year. In 2006, Thai organizer sector consumption accounted for a value of approximately 1,488 billion Baht, which was almost 19% of the GDP, and the value of imported energy was greater than 912 billion Baht. [1]

In order to cope with the rapidly increasing demand on energy in Thailand, on September, the Master Plan for State education Sector Reform for transforming state enterprises in Thailand received the cabinet's approval in order to reduce financial burdens as well as to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of major organizer sector sectors. [2] This plan

aims at reforming and privatizing key utility and infrastructure sectors in Thailand. Of these, the energy sector is one of the four key sectors that are given priority in the reform policy

The Good Membership Behavior in Organization of the state enterprise reform policy in Thailand has led to a major process change in the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, with the objectives of increasing effectiveness, efficiency and shareholder's value. The process requires a sharp change in ownership, strategy, power structures and control of the organization. These changes are expected to have a profound impact, not only on the economic and financial results of the companies, but also on the human factors: individual employees, human resource management practices, and organizational commitment. [3]

As described in the organizational commitment management and behavioral science literature, organizational commitment is considered as a key factor in the relationship between individuals and organizations. Organizational commitment refers to the degree of loyalty shown by employees towards their organization. Employees are regarded as committed to an organization if they willingly continue their association with the organization and devote considerable effort to achieving organizational goals. Higher levels of effort exerted by employees (by greater levels of organizational commitment) lead to higher levels of performance and effectiveness at both the individual and the organizational level, moreover, point out that organizational commitment, if properly managed, could lead to beneficial consequences, such as organizational effectiveness, improved performance, and reduced turnover and absenteeism. This quest to harness potential organizational benefits has resulted in the large number of studies that focus on the nature of organizational commitment. [2]

The Good Membership Behavior in Organization policy for the education sector in Thailand also has led to organizational changes in public energy enterprises. According to the literature review, some organizational changes could affect employees' organizational commitment in both positive and negative ways. Major organizational changes include changing human resource management practices, change-related behaviors, [4] and work-related values (cultures) in organizations. This research therefore is oriented toward systematically examining the current organizational variables and the forms of education organizer as shaped by the organizational commitment policy.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Good Membership Behavior

It is easy to be confused when we talk about behavioral theory of leadership, as some people may think it is how a leader behaves. To some extent that's true, but there are specific areas or categories of behavior that are focused on when discussing the behavioral theory of leadership? Those areas are: Autocratic leaders: Leaders that exhibit this behavior make decisions without consulting their teams. The old saying 'it is my way or the highway' is a good example of this type of leadership behavior. It is not a bad behavioral aspect, as sometimes there are situations where fast, decisive decisions need to be made, and an autocratic leader typically makes those. Democratic leaders: [3] A democratic leader involves his or her team members and seeks to get consensus or feedback from his or her team. This works best when a team is working together and the leader wants or needs the input of others. For example, a sales manager may ask for assistance from an engineer in order to make an informed, accurate decision.

Laissez-faire leaders: This leadership behavior allows the people in the team to make the decisions. The best situation for this type of leadership behavior is when a team is very capable of doing the job or jobs that they need to do. If there is a team of scientists and they know what they have to do, a laissez-faire leader will stay out of their way. [4]

B. Organizational Commitment

Described commitment, in general, as a disposition to engage in "consistent lines of activity" (p. 33) as a result of the accumulation of "side bets"¹ that would be lost if the activity were discontinued. When used to explain commitment to the organization, the consistent line of activity refers to maintaining membership (i.e., employment) in the organization. The term side bet has been applied quite loosely in this context. Generally, it has been used to refer to anything of value the individual has invested (e.g., time, effort, money) that would be lost or deemed worthless at some perceived cost to the individual if he or she were to leave the organization. Such investments might include contributions to no vested pension plans, development of organization-specific skills or status, use of organizational benefits such as reduced mortgage rates, and so on. The perceived cost of leaving may be exacerbated by a perceived lack of alternatives to replace or make up for the foregone investments. At any rate, it is the threat of loss that commits the person to the organization. [5]

This and similar views of commitment can be labeled continuance commitment. Continuance commitment is generally believed to develop on the basis of an economic calculation clearly; however, this is not the only way to view commitment. Other investigators conceptualize commitment as an affective or emotional orientation to an entity, in this case, the organization. We will refer to this as affective commitment. Affectively committed employees remain with

the organization for its own sake, apart from its purely instrumental worth". [4]

The importance of this distinction will become apparent in the proposed reinterpretation of the findings. It should be noted that these two forms of commitment are conceptualized here as being independent. That is, the extent to which one is affectively committed does not affect the degree of continuance commitment and vice versa. In a recent book on the psychology of commitment and other employee-organization linkage variables, and an extensive review of the theoretical and empirical work done on the concept of organizational commitment. [6] Because of this recent effort, a similarly extensive review of commitment is not undertaken here. However, summarize much of the previous empirical research on organizational commitment as an independent and a dependent variable respectively lists the different definitions of commitment that have been used in earlier work on this topic.

Commitment has been significantly, negatively associated with turnover and, to a lesser extent, with other withdrawal behaviors such as decreased performance and increased absenteeism and tardiness. With the exception of the study that assessed lifetime commitment norms and values among Japanese workers, the studies in report significant correlations between commitment and turnover ranging from several of these studies employed longitudinal designs with as many as four time-period measures. Most of these studies used the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire, developed by, as the measure of the independent variable. This measure, because of its popularity and continued use, has in a sense become "the" approach to organizational commitment.

A larger body of work has focused on the antecedents of commitment, and several important classifications of variables have emerged from this stream of research. Specifically, psychological variables such as identification, role related variables such as role conflict/ambiguity, and early work experiences such as the degree of job challenge have all been found to be antecedents of commitment. Some researchers also have found that side bets or sunk costs increase the commitment felt by long term organization members. In addition, have the demonstrated empirical support in a field setting for the attribution nature of commitment. Their work indicates that commitment results from irrevocable and volitional acts that the individual engages in during the job choice process. [7] This approach, then, links the development of organizational commitment with pre-organizational entry phenomena.

Despite the substantial number of studies that have investigated the antecedents of organizational commitment, this literature is still characterized by a "laundry list" of significant antecedent or correlate variables. That is, though the literature is fairly clear with respect to the outcomes of commitment (i.e., decreased turnover and other forms of withdrawal), the antecedents of commitment seem to be much more varied and inconsistent. This inconsistency may stem from the several different ways in which commitment has

been defined and operationalized. To the extent that there is a lack of consistency in the definition of the concept, it follows that its antecedents would be similarly inconsistent. [4]

III. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employed a questionnaire as a quantitative method. The respondents were 305 faculties and staffs of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. This research used Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test, One-Way Anova Analysis of Variance, and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in data analysis.[2]

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS

The study on the perceptions of staffs of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University regarding the presence of attributes of organizational commitment evidenced significant results. The findings of the study revealed that the totally state-owned education organizer has mean scores which demonstrated less emphasis on affective commitment and normative commitment compared to partially transformed and totally good membership behavior, whereas their mean scores on continuance commitment were not different in these enterprises. These findings partially confirmed the hypotheses of the study, which were consistent with the literature. To summarize the research hypotheses formulated and the findings with regard to the hypotheses of the study. [4]

TABLE I
DESCRIPTION OF GOOD MEMBERSHIP BEHAVIOR

Good Membership Behavior	Mean	Interpretation
1. Assistance	3.60	Effective
2. Consideration for others	3.64	Effective
3. Tolerance	3.67	Effective
4. Cooperation	3.96	Effective
5. Responsible	3.85	Effective
Overall Mean	3.74	Effective

The findings disclosed that the majority were male between 25-34 years old, married and live together. The majority had an undergraduate degree working for private companies. The average income of the respondents was

between 10,001 -20,000 baht. The respondents rated the Good Membership Behavior of Assistance, Consideration for others, tolerance, Cooperation and the Responsible as high. For every three months, the average Cooperation was 3.96. The average Tolerance was about 3.67. In addition, differences in sex, age, income, education, marital status, and working period revealed differences in being good membership behavior. The results also indicated that organizational commitment was significantly related to being good membership behavior. [6]

It is evidenced that, from the results of the levels of some types of organizational commitment of employees in Good Membership Behavior are different to a certain extent. The level of employees' affective commitment and normative commitment in the Good Membership Behavior is higher than that of partially transformed and non-transformed Good Membership Behavior. [7] Nevertheless, the differences of the level of employees' continuance commitment in all public organizations were not statistically significant. In addition, the analysis of variance results suggested that when demographic variables accounted for the covariates, organization type effects for affective and normative commitments remain strong. The first and significant observation drawn from the results of this study is that there is a significant difference in the level of some attributes of organizational commitment between three types of public energy enterprises. The lack of a structural type difference holds for only continuance commitment.

Since implementing a public reform policy can result in several forms of partial- or full privatized organization, it leads to the question of whether organization structure matters to performance and commitment. The degree of interaction between parties (groups of employee) to exchange in organizations influences the relational cohesion and organizational commitment of each party. If structuring depersonalized the exchange, commitment should fall. Although there is evidence that bureaucratic structuring increases commitment in voluntary associations the results of this study have partly supported the previous studies that bureaucratic structuring is negatively related to organizational commitment. [5]

The results of the finding for the fourth confirmed that the transformed organization had higher mean scores in the employees' perceptions of the reform policy and change-related communications in their organization than both partially transformed and non-transformed organizations. Employees in the transformed public enterprise have been found to have favorable attitudes toward the implementation of the State Enterprise Reform. According to in-depth interviews, the transformed organization prioritizes the importance of communication as well as implements these communications effectively at all levels in their organization. Effective communications on changes would also improve their management and organizational practices

The findings for the fifth hypothesis revealed that the employees' perceived most of the human resource management [5] practices at different levels in the Good

Membership Behavior. Statistically significant differences were found between three types of Organizational Commitment will including Mindset, Remain with the organization, Norm in five HRM practices, including the payment system, reward and recognition, supervisor effectiveness, training and development, and employee participation. Those in the transformed organizations – both partially and totally – had higher mean scores than those in the non-transformed organization for the above- mentioned factors. Moreover, it can be observed that the employee participation mean score in the totally transformed Good Membership Behavior was the highest. [6]

V. DISCUSSION

The results of Good Membership Behavior including assistance, Consideration for others, tolerance, Cooperation Responsible indicated a moderate negative coefficient of $-.49$, estimation of the structural equation model at a statistically significant level greater than $.10$. These findings suggest that when change-related behaviors are present in the workplace, employees' organizational commitment decreases. These change-related behaviors were proved to have a negative impact on organizational [6] commitment. This negative relationship is consistent with the findings at the estimation of the structural equation model at a statistically significant level greater than $.10$, the finding for the eighth hypothesis revealed a moderate positive coefficient of $.46$. The results suggest that when human resource management practices are present in the workplace, employees' organizational commitment increases. Hence, the HRM practices were predicted to have a positive impact on organizational commitment. The results of this study support the previous empirical evidence.

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

In addition, the results suggest some remarkable managerial implications for each type of the Good Membership Behavior. Successful reformed Organizational Commitment depends largely on competitive environments, leaders' initiatives, and supports from the government. Without such supports, public officials might have difficulty implementing specific measures, i.e., a marketable payment system, equitable rewards, effective leadership, extensive training and development, employee participation, effective communications, etc. – that encourage employee commitment. [7] After implementing the Good Membership Behavior policy, political supports should be ongoing and evolving in order to be certain that specific measures are implemented continuously by the public organizations. Nonetheless, some Good Membership Behavior may require partially-owned form. This structure is advantageous in terms of improving the cultures and values of the Good Membership Behavior & Organizational Commitment by applying private management practices and in terms of being under company control to implement development policies.

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